

OXIDATION OF RESORCINOL BY HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN PRESENCE OF TUNGSTIC ACID SOL AS CATALYST.

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Oxidation of resorcinol by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of tungstic acid sol has been carried out. The nature of the end-products and also the kinetics of the reaction have been studied.

The author in his previous publications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938 18, 291) has carried out the oxidation of some of the phenols by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of tungstic acid and molybdic acid sols. In this paper, the oxidation of resorcinol by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of tungstic acid sol has been described.

As end-products of the reaction, carbon dioxide and maleic acid have been found out. Carbon dioxide has been estimated quantitatively by absorbing in dry soda-lime. It has been found that 137.3 mg. resorcinol gives 107 mg. carbon dioxide. Maleic acid has been extracted with ether after the reaction is complete.

The mechanism of the reaction as regards the intermediate products and also any other final products are in the course of investigation. The equation may be finally expressed as

Measurement of Kinetics.

Resorcinol of chemically pure grade (Merck) was taken and dissolved in water. In all our experiments we used redistilled water and Scherring-Kahlbaum's hydrogen peroxide. The sol was prepared by the addition of hydrochloric acid to sodium tungstate which reacts according to the equation

In order to study the kinetics, the pressure of carbon dioxide developed during the course of the experiment was measured at constant volume using high concentration of hydrogen peroxide. To determine the velocity coefficient the following expression was used

$$k = \frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \cdot \log \frac{P_\infty - P_{t_1}}{P_\infty - P_{t_2}},$$

where P_{t_1} is the pressure in cm. of mercury at any time t_1 (in minutes) and P_{t_2} is the the pressure at time t_2 , P_∞ is the pressure that should develop when the reaction is complete. It may be obtained by means of the equation

$$X = h \frac{V_a \frac{273}{T} + V_{ra}}{P_0},$$

where X = the volume of gas evolved in c.mm. at N. T. P. which may be easily obtained from the amount of carbon dioxide formed. The amount of carbon dioxide can be calculated from the equation (i) or experimentally determined by absorbing in soda-lime.

h = corresponding reading of the manometer = P_∞ .

V_0 = the volume of the gas space in the vessel.

T = absolute temperature of the water bath. V_0 = volume of the liquid in the vessel, a = the solubility of carbon dioxide in the liquid of the vessel at N.T.P. = 0.759 (Bohr, *Ann. Phys. Chem.*, 1899, 88, 504). P_0 = normal pressure = 760 mm. mercury.

The experiments were carried out in a Warburg-Barcroft apparatus. The increase of pressure due to the production of carbon dioxide was indicated by a manometer, filled with mercury. The total volume up to the constant mercury level in the manometer was 48.4 c.c. and was determined by filling the vessel and the tube with mercury. The reaction mixture occupied 10 c.c. No carbon dioxide was formed by the action of hydrogen peroxide on resorcinol in absence of the sol. The whole system was shaken 55 to 60 times per minute throughout the experiment. The vessels were completely immersed in a big thermostat which was maintained at the required temperature. To correct for the changes of temperature and the barometric pressure a similar vessel which contained only water was used. It was always observed by keeping strict control in which the carbon dioxide was absorbed by caustic potash in a suitable reservoir that there was very slight spontaneous decomposition of hydrogen peroxide during the course of the experiment. The experimental results are given below.

TABLE I.

Effect of varying the conc. of resorcinol.
Temp. = 28°. $p_a = 1.18$. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$.
Sodium tungstate = 0.01M.

Resorcinol (M)	0.00625	0.0125	0.025
k (mean)	0.0015	0.0017	0.0018

TABLE II.

Effect of varying the conc. of H_2O_2
Temp. = 28°. $p_a = 1.18$. Resorcinol = 0.025M.
Sodium tungstate = 0.01M.

H_2O_2 (M)	0.18	0.36	0.72	1.08
k (mean)	0.0011	0.0015	0.0018	0.0020

TABLE III.

Effect of varying the conc. of sodium tungstate.
Temp. = 28°. $p_a = 1.18$. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$.
Resorcinol = 0.025M.

Sodium tungstate (M)	0.005	0.01	0.015	0.02
k (mean)	0.0011	0.0018	0.0024	0.0029

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the p_a .
Temp. = 28°. Resorcinol = 0.025M.
 $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$. Sodium tungstate = 0.01M.

p_a	1.18	1.5	4.3
k	0.0018	0.0019	0.0017

The oxidation can similarly be carried out in presence of molybdic acid sol.

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